

Studies on Coagulation and Electrical Properties of Prussian Blue, Silver Ferrocyanide, and Aluminium Oxide Hydrosols

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The ζ -potentials, corrected for surface-conductance effect, and the concentration of the equicoagulating counter ions, beyond which surface-conductance effect does not exist for Prussian blue, silver ferrocyanide, and three varieties of aluminium oxide sols, have been calculated. The coagulation of these sols are described in the light of the equation:

$$\zeta_a = A + B \log \Sigma c_i$$

(where ζ_a represents the measured ζ -potential at a total equicoagulating electrolyte concentration of Σc_i , and A and B are constants).

Prussian blue, silver ferrocyanide, and three varieties of aluminium oxide sols have been prepared in order to study the dependence of their ζ -potentials on the concentrations of the added counter ions and also to correct the values of these potentials for surface-conductance effect.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a). *Aluminium Oxide Sols*.—The transparent jelly of hydrated aluminium oxide, obtained by addition of liquor ammonia (E. Merck) to a concentrated solution of AlCl_3 (E. Merck), was broken down by shaking it with water and the precipitate was repeatedly washed with conductivity water, following the method of decantation. The precipitate was then divided into two parts. A transparent sol (sol 1) was obtained by peptising the first part with 1.5*N* acetic acid solution, whereas the second part yielded an opaque sol (sol 2) on peptisation with 0.5*N* acetic acid solution. Acetic acid, from both the sols, was removed by heating on a water bath, followed by dialysis. A portion of sol 2 was diluted three times. This resulted in a new sol (sol 3). The sols were stored in Jena bottles and allowed to age for 15 days. Sols 1, 2, and 3 were found to possess sp. conductance of 3.692×10^{-4} , 1.852×10^{-4} , and 6.105×10^{-5} $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25° and solid material contents of 18.7, 18.1 and 5.2 g./litre, respectively. The sols were positively charged.

(b). *Prussian Blue Sol*.—The negatively charged sol was prepared by addition of 1.5% FeCl_3 (Riedel) solution to an excess of 2% $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (E. Merck) solution, followed by dialysis. The sol was stored in a Jena bottle and allowed to age for one month. The sp. conductance and the solid material content of the sol were found to be 2.389×10^{-4} $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25° and 5.8 g./litre, respectively.

(c). *Silver Ferrocyanide Sol*.—The sol was prepared by peptising a precipitate, thoroughly washed with water, of silver ferrocyanide, obtained by addition of 1.5% solution

of AgNO_3 (E. Merck) to an excess of 1.2% $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution, with a dilute (0.1%) solution of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, followed by dialysis. The sol was kept at 15° in a refrigerator in order to check any probable decomposition and allowed to age for 15 days. The composition of the sol was confirmed to be $\text{KAg}_5\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ as suggested by Kleibs' by determining the Fe:Ag ratio. The negatively charged sol was found to have a sp. conductance of 9.703×10^{-4} ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ at 25° and a solid material content of 10.92 g./litre.

Determination of Equicoagulating and Equigelating Concentrations of Electrolytes and Measurement of ζ -Potential.—The equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes for different sols (except Al_2O_3 sols 1 and 2) were determined in the rapid zone of coagulation exactly in the same way as described by Kundu and Moulik³. The equigelating concentrations of electrolytes for Al_2O_3 sols 1 and 2 were determined by addition of 0.5 ml of the electrolyte to 2 ml of the sol followed by testing for gelation after 15 min. Different charged counter ions were employed in each case.

The ζ -potentials of Prussian blue, silver ferrocyanide, and aluminium oxide sol 3 were measured at equicoagulating concentrations of different counter ions by electro-osmotic and microcutaphoretic experiments, as described by Mukherjee *et al.*², and Chakravarti and Ghosh³, respectively. The procedure adopted in the cases of aluminium oxide sols 1 and 2 was different as in these cases a rigid gel was produced on addition of electrolytes which remained unchanged even when subjected to centrifuging at a speed of 2000 r.p.m. A definite volume of the sol was mixed with the calculated volume of the equigelating electrolyte and the mixture was introduced and allowed to set inside the U-tube. This was used as diaphragm. Instead of the supernatant liquid (not available in this case), a solution of the same counter ion having the same sp. conductance as that of the diaphragm was used. The Smoluchowski equation was used for calculation of the ζ -potential.

DISCUSSION

The results obtained have been plotted in Fig. 1 and 2 which show that a decreasing concentration of the electrolyte, and hence decreasing sp. conductance (S) of the supernatant liquid, causes the ζ -potential to decrease. The ζ -potential values corrected for surface-conductance effect are determined from the intercepts of $1/\zeta_a$ vs. $1/S$ plots on the $1/\zeta_a$ axis in accordance with Ghosh's equations⁴⁻⁵ for electro-osmosis:

$$1/\zeta_a = 1/\zeta + (m/S) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

and for electrophoresis;

$$1/\zeta_a = 1/\zeta + (m'/S) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Different methods of measurements are found to yield nearly the same values of the corrected ζ -potential for the same sol. The difference between the corrected ζ -values for

1. *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1955, 10, 244.
2. *This Journal*, 1927, 4, 493.
3. *Ibid.*, 1959, 36, 171.
4. Ghosh, *Naturwiss.*, 1955, 5, 121; *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 402.
5. Ghosh *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 29.
6. *Ibid.*, 1956, 42, 705.

aluminium oxide sols 1 and 2 may be attributed to the difference in particle size and hence surface roughness.

FIG. 1

I. Al_2O_3 sol 1:	III. Al_2O_3 sol 3. Electro-	V. Prussian blue sol. Elec-	VII. Silver ferrocyanide
1—KCl	osmosis:	tro-osmosis:	sol. Electro-osmosis:
2—KCl + K_2SO_4	1, 2, 3—KCl + K_2SO_4	1—KCl + $La(NO_3)_3$	1, 2— KNO_3 + $Ba(NO_3)_2$
3— K_2SO_4	4— K_2SO_4	5— $La(NO_3)_3$	3— $BaCl_2$
4— K_2SO_4 + $K_3Fe(CN)_6$	5— $K_3Fe(CN)_6$	VI: Prussian blue sol.	4— $Ba(NO_3)_2$
5— $K_3Fe(CN)_6$	IV. Al_2O_3 sol 3. Microcata-	Microcataphoresis:	5— $AlCl_3$
II. Al_2O_3 sol 2:	phoresis:	1—KCl + $La(NO_3)_3$	6— $Al(NO_3)_3$
1—KCl	1— CH_3COONa	5— $La(NO_3)_3$	VIII. Silver ferrocyanide
2, 3—KCl + K_2SO_4	2, 3, 4—KCl + K_2SO_4		sol. Microcataphoresis:
4— K_2SO_4	5— K_2SO_4		1—KCl + $BaCl_2$
5— K_2SO_4 + $K_3Fe(CN)_6$	6— $K_3Fe(CN)_6$		2, 3— KNO_3 + $Ba(NO_3)_2$
6— $K_3Fe(CN)_6$			4— $Ba(NO_3)_2$
			5— $Al(NO_3)_3$

The equation proposed by Kundu and Moulik⁶ for the concentration dependence of ζ -potential is expressed as

$$\zeta_a = A + B \log \Sigma c_1 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where Σc_1 represents the total concentration in normality of the equicoagulating counter ions and A and B are constants. According to equation (3), a straight line should be obtained when ζ_a values are plotted against $\log \Sigma c_1$. As is evident from Fig. 1, this expectation is fully corroborated.

All the equations have been derived, taking surface conductance into consideration. Therefore a combination of these three equations may provide the limiting concentration value beyond which ζ -potential will cease to increase. This concentration is found from the graph by extrapolating the ζ_a - $\log \Sigma c_1$ curve up to ζ obtained from equations (1) and (2).

In the previous communication⁵, nothing was said about the constants A and B . From equation(3), it is clear that A is a constant for a particular sol and B is also constant but for a particular method of determination of ζ -potential for a particular sol, because it relates to the slope of the $\zeta_a - \log \Sigma c_i$ straight line and ζ_a is different for different methods of measurements. These constants evidently play some important role in the determination of equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes (*vide infra*).

As regards coagulation, wide deviations from Verwey and Overbeek's inverse sixth power rule are observed in the case of these sols. Overbeek⁷ himself has pointed out that some deviations are actually found in cases of many electrolytes. From equation (3) above, one may write

$$\Sigma c_i = e^{(\zeta_a - A)/B} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Now Σc_i , which represents the total equicoagulating concentration in normality, is completely determined with the knowledge of the values of A and B which are found from the graphs, ζ_a being known from experiments. Equation (4) shows that the concentration of the electrolyte, which will bring coagulation of a particular sol in a particular time, not only depends on the charge of the counter ion but also on its ability to affect the ζ -potential, or, in other words, on its ability to increase or decrease the surface conductance.

FIG. 2
(Description of graphs and points are as in Fig. 1).

It is a common fact that the increase of surface conductance means a decrease in the ζ -potential. The decreasing Σc_i values in the cases described are found to decrease the ζ -potentials and hence increase the surface conductance. As the overall effect is a decrease in the ζ -value, this may be described as an equivalent decrease in the thickness of the double layer which automatically means a decrease in the ζ -potential. Evidently the concentration of the equicoagulating electrolyte depends, apart from the valency of the counter ion, on the ζ -potential of the particles of the sol at that concentration and is completely determined by equation (4).

7. "Colloid Science," Vol. I, edited by H. R. Krumb, Elsevier, 1960, p. 311.

TABLE I

Sol.	Corrected ζ -potential (mv).			Limiting concentration (N).			Δ (mv).		$\frac{2.303B}{(mv/\log B)}$		
	(I).	(II).	Mean.	(I).	(II).	Mean.	(I).	(II).	(I).	(II).	
Aluminium oxide sol 1	..	42.5	..	1.26×10^{-4}	..	1.26×10^{-4}	52.2	..	52.2	5.1	..
Do sol 2	..	37.6	..	2.69×10^{-4}	..	2.69×10^{-4}	42.6	..	42.6	3.2	..
Do sol 3	..	26.3	27.1	2.09×10^{-4}	2.63×10^{-4}	2.36×10^{-4}	40.5	40.5	40.5	8.5	8.5
Prussian blue sol	..	21.1	20.8	1.66×10^{-4}	1.26×10^{-4}	1.46×10^{-4}	35.5	35.3	35.4	9.1	7.9
Silver ferrocyanide sol	..	45.9	44.7	2.04×10^{-4}	6.03×10^{-5}	1.34×10^{-4}	57.7	58.4	58.1	14.2	14.1

N.B.—(I) and (II) denote respectively by electro-osmosis and microcataphoresis.

The ζ -potential values, corrected for surface-conductance effect, the limiting concentrations of the counter ions, beyond which surface conductance will play no part in the determination of ζ -potential, and the values of the constants A and B for different sols and for different methods of measurements are recorded in Table I.

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